

Ultrasonic studies of resorcinol in protic and aprotic solvents at 40°

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Various acoustical parameters like adiabatic compressibility (κ_s), specific impedance (Z), intermolecular free path (L_f), Rao's molar sound function (R), relaxation strength (r), the Van der Waals constant (b), internal pressure (π), solvation number (S_n) etc., of resorcinol solutions (0.1–1.0 mol dm⁻³) in water, methanol, tetrahydrofuran (THF) and 1,4-dioxane have been determined from ultrasonic sound velocity (2 MHz), density and viscosity data at 40°. The parameters are correlated with concentration and interpreted in the light of molecular interactions occurring in solutions. It is observed that solvent structure especially in water and methanol systems is disrupted and new structure is formed with resorcinol molecules and chain-like structure is formed in 1,4-dioxane system.

Physicochemical behavior and molecular interactions occurring in a variety of liquid mixtures¹ and solutions can be studied with the aid of ultrasonic sound velocity, density and viscosity data. In continuation with our work², an attempt is made in the present study to understand the structure and molecular interactions occurring in different solutions of resorcinol in water, methanol, dioxane and THF.

Results and Discussion

The experimental data on ultrasonic velocity (U), density (ρ) and viscosity (η) of pure solvents : water, methanol, 1,4-dioxane and THF and resorcinol solutions at 40° are presented in Table 1.

In order to understand molecular interactions occurring in the solutions, various parameters like specific acoustic impedance (Z), adiabatic compressibility³ (κ_s), intermolecular free length⁴ (L_f), internal pressure⁵ (π), relaxation strength⁶ (r), Rao's molar sound function⁷ (R), molar compressibility⁸ (W), Van der Waal's constant⁹ (b), solvation number¹⁰ (S_n) etc. were calculated at 40° by standard eqn. reported earlier¹¹. Some of these parameters are reported in Table 2.

Correlation equations and coefficients for some parameters are given in Table 3. Linear increase of U (Fig. 1), Z , W , R and b (correlation coefficient $\gamma = 0.9776$ – 0.9997), and linear decrease of k_s , L_f , π and r (correlation coefficient $\gamma = 0.9781$ – 0.9992) with concentration (Table 2) suggest that powerful solvent-solute interaction occur in the solution¹². The decrease in π and L_f furnishes decrease in cohesive forces. The decrease in cohesive forces are due to structure-breaking tendency of the solute¹¹. In water and methanol systems, self-association (H-bonding) is disrupted

by solute molecules and thereby formation of new H-bonding between solute and solvent molecules has occurred.

Table 1. Variation of ρ , U , and η with concentration of resorcinol in different solvents at 40°

Concn. M	ρ gm cm^{-3}	$U \times 10^{-5}$ cm s^{-1}	$\eta \times 10^2$ poise
		Water	
0.0	1.0000	1.5108	0.6600
0.0997	1.0027	1.5187	0.6821
0.1983	1.0055	1.5220	0.7006
0.4005	1.0063	1.5235	0.7299
0.6012	1.0089	1.5245	0.7600
0.7989	1.0166	1.5272	0.8347
1.0035	1.0221	1.5293	0.8738
		Methanol	
0.0	0.7914	1.0827	0.4693
0.1013	0.7983	1.0908	0.4820
0.1995	0.8012	1.1092	0.4977
0.4010	0.8068	1.1108	0.5371
0.5989	0.8197	1.1276	0.5743
0.8019	0.8271	1.1432	0.6181
0.9992	0.8391	1.1544	0.6702
		Dioxane	
0.0	1.0332	1.3178	1.0014
0.0988	1.0375	1.3240	1.0390
0.2015	1.0389	1.3258	1.0818
0.3991	1.0450	1.3374	1.1639
0.5904	1.0478	1.3451	1.2304
0.8008	1.0543	1.3570	1.3883
1.0080	1.0594	1.3657	1.5220
		THF	
0.0	0.8902	1.2772	0.5015
0.1010	0.8969	1.2803	0.5221
0.2025	0.9009	1.2836	0.5711
0.3978	0.9096	1.2989	0.6091
0.6081	0.9185	1.3097	0.6662
0.7993	0.9271	1.3175	0.7313
1.0017	0.9327	1.3302	0.7992

Table 2. Variation of Z , k_s , L_f , π , r and S_n with concentration of resorcinol in different solvents at 40°

Concn. M	$Z \times 10^{-5}$ $g\ cm^{-2}$	$k_s \times 10^{11}$ $cm^2\ dyne^{-1}$	L_f Å^0	π	r	S_n
Water						
0.0	1.5108	4.3811	0.4025	2442.34	0.1084	-
0.0997	1.5197	4.3328	0.4003	2327.29	0.0990	6.16
0.1983	1.5304	4.2933	0.3985	2222.95	0.0951	6.83
0.4005	1.5331	4.2814	0.3979	2028.95	0.0933	12.28
0.6012	1.5381	4.2648	0.3972	1873.34	0.9210	16.13
0.7989	1.5526	4.2175	0.3950	1799.98	0.0888	15.54
1.0035	1.5631	4.1833	0.3933	1698.07	0.0864	16.36
MeOH						
0.0	0.8568	10.7796	0.6314	1063.77	0.5421	-
0.1013	0.8708	10.5279	0.6240	1039.36	0.5352	2.06
0.1995	0.8887	10.1447	0.6125	1011.62	0.5194	1.65
0.4010	0.8962	10.0453	0.6095	983.53	0.5180	2.92
0.5989	0.9243	9.5948	0.5957	957.21	0.5033	2.74
0.8019	0.9455	9.2512	0.5849	934.41	0.4895	2.89
0.9992	0.9687	8.9428	0.5751	925.67	0.4794	3.05
DO						
0.0	1.3616	5.5732	0.4540	518.33	0.3216	-
0.0988	1.3737	5.4984	0.4510	525.09	0.3152	1.00
0.2015	1.3774	5.4761	0.4500	534.26	0.3154	1.55
0.3991	1.3976	5.3501	0.4448	550.55	0.3013	1.37
0.5904	1.4094	5.2749	0.4417	562.03	0.2932	1.39
0.8008	1.4307	5.1508	0.4365	593.33	0.2807	1.50
1.0080	1.4468	5.0609	0.4326	617.64	0.2714	1.58
THF						
0.0	1.1370	6.8864	0.5047	425.17	0.3628	-
0.1010	1.1483	6.8019	0.5016	432.18	0.3597	1.55
0.2025	1.1564	6.7412	0.4993	449.41	0.3568	1.82
0.3978	1.1815	6.5163	0.4909	457.65	0.3410	1.45
0.6081	1.2030	6.3471	0.4845	473.05	0.3300	1.51
0.7993	1.2215	6.2140	0.4794	490.49	0.3220	1.65
1.0017	1.2407	6.0593	0.4734	505.50	0.3088	1.70

The presence of molecular interaction is further supported by the solvation number (Fig. 2). From Fig. 2, it is clear that the solvation is higher in water system and least in THF and dioxane. Due to high polarity of water, solvent-solute interactions take place to greater extent thereby increasing the solvation number at lower concentration of the solute. At higher concentration, solute-solute interaction dominates thereby change in solvation is less. In methanol, solvation number is much lesser than that of water but higher than in dioxane and THF. In methanol, S_n decreases to minimum (0.2 mol dm⁻³) and then increases almost linearly with concentration above 0.4 mol dm⁻³. While in dioxane, it decreases up to 0.4 mol dm⁻³ and then remains almost constant with concentration. In THF, it increases in the beginning then decreases at 0.4 mol dm⁻³ and then increases very slightly with concentration. The minimum values of solvation number in dioxane and THF may be due to the presence of lone-pair of electrons which associates with the OH group of resorcinol. It is expected that in

Fig. 1. Variation of ultrasonic velocity with resorcinol concentration in different solvents.

dioxane, due to two oxygen groups, a linear chain-like structure is formed. Further, the polarity of all the four solvents are in the order : water > methanol > THF > dioxane. The solvation numbers are also in the same order. The decrease in S_n might be due to disruption of solvent structure. The resultant values of S_n decided on the basis of the dipole-dipole interaction. The dipole-dipole interaction of

Fig. 2. Variation of solvation number with resorcinol concentration in different solvents.

opposite type favour association while of the same type disrupt the structure formed previously. In the present case, it is expected that dipole-dipole interaction of opposite type may be much stronger than of the same type, which may be reflected in increase of S_n with concentration.

Table 3. Correlation coefficient (γ) and correlation equations for resorcinol in different solvents

Parameter	Correlation coefficient γ	Correlation equation
Water		
ρ (g cm ⁻³)	0.9637	$\rho - 0.0206C = 0.9997$
$U \times 10^5$ (cm s ⁻¹)	0.9776	$U - 1053.699C = 1.5188$
$Z \times 10^5$ (g cm ⁻² s ⁻¹)	0.9762	$Z - 4418.63C = 1.5167$
$k_s \times 10^{-11}$ (cm ² dyne ⁻¹)	0.9788	$k_s + 1.5C = 4.34$
r	0.9780	$r + 0.01957C = 0.0989$
L_f	0.9781	$L_f + 0.0071C = 0.4007$
Methanol		
ρ (g cm ⁻³)	0.9926	$\rho - 0.0456C = 0.7918$
$U \times 10^5$ (cm s ⁻¹)	0.9828	$U - 6656.438C = 1.0883$
$Z \times 10^5$ (g cm ⁻² s ⁻¹)	0.9929	$Z - 10571.51C = 0.8611$
$k_s \times 10^{-11}$ (cm ² dyne ⁻¹)	0.9899	$k_s + 1.7C = 10.60$
r	0.9834	$r + 0.0585C = 0.5377$
L_f	0.9903	$L_f + 0.0522C = 0.6272$
Dioxane		
ρ (g cm ⁻³)	0.9955	$\rho - 0.0245C = 1.0345$
$U \times 10^5$ (cm s ⁻¹)	0.9973	$U - 4788.993C = 1.3178$
$Z \times 10^5$ (g cm ⁻² s ⁻¹)	0.9969	$Z - 8300.822C = 1.3630$
$k_s \times 10^{-11}$ (cm ² dyne ⁻¹)	0.9974	$k_s + 5.0C = 5.56$
r	0.9972	$\rho + 0.0503C = 0.3218$
L_f	0.9974	$L_f + 0.0209C = 0.4536$
THF		
ρ (g cm ⁻³)	0.9979	$\rho - 0.0410C = 0.8931$
$U \times 10^5$ (cm s ⁻¹)	0.9958	$U - 5592.329C = 1.2744$
$Z \times 10^5$ (g cm ⁻² s ⁻¹)	0.9985	$Z - 10462.47C = 1.1377$
$k_s \times 10^{-11}$ (cm ² dyne ⁻¹)	0.9966	$k_s + 0.84C = 6.88$
r	0.9960	$r + 0.0569C = 0.3658$
L_f	0.9971	$L_f + 0.0318C = 0.5046$

On the basis of experimental findings, it may be concluded that molecular interactions (solvent-solute) is predominant in water system. The self-association in water and methanol is disrupted and new association with solute molecules is formed. The structure-forming tendency of solute is more pronounced in water and methanol.

Experimental

The solvents used in the present study were purified by appropriate methods prior to use¹³. Water was triple-distilled. Methanol, THF and 1,4-dioxane (all of special grade) were fractionally distilled. Purity was better than 99.95–

99.97%, checked by GLC and moisture detection. By measuring the density and viscosity, the purity of liquids was further checked which were in good agreement with the literature values. For all the solvents, the solutions (0.1–1.0 mol dm⁻³) were prepared by dissolving resorcinol in each solvent.

Ultrasonic velocity (U), viscosity (η) and density (ρ) of pure solvents and solutions were measured by using M-82 multifrequency interferometer operating at 2 MHz, suspended level Ubbelohde viscometer and pycnometer at 40 ± 0.1° with an accuracy of ± 0.1%, ± 0.05% and 0.0001 g cm⁻³, respectively.

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